

CESSDA Widening Activities 2018

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<p>Abstract: As a continuation of SaW project assessment of the situation in European countries regarding state of the art data archive data service, the CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 includes the report on current and recent / new development, and addressing persistent obstacles to progress. The activity consist of adapting the System of monitoring, developed during SaW project, to enable flexible and continuous monitoring of Countries progressing toward CESSDA membership.</p>	
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History

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ADP	Arhiv Družboslovnih Podatkov
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
ČSDA	Czech Social Science Data Archive
DAS	Data Archive Service
DMP	Data Management Plan
EU	European Union
FORS	Swiss Foundation for Research in Social Sciences
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NDP	National Development Plan
NOAD	National Open Access Desk
OA	OpenAIRE
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
SND	Swedish National Data Service
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
TÁRKI	TÁRKI Alapítvány (TARKI Foundation)

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1. Introduction

1.1 About the CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project and role of the country reports

As a continuation of SaW project assessment of the situation in European countries regarding state of the art data archive data service, the CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 includes the report on current and recent / new development, and addresses persistent obstacles to progress. The activity consist of adapting the System of monitoring, developed during SaW project, to enable flexible and continuous monitoring of Countries progressing toward CESSDA membership. The monitoring system includes part devoted to Collection of information about the needs of the CESSDA non-member partner institutions, that is subtask of the Widening 2018, led by TARKI.

1.2 Previous studies

Results and reports from previous Widening activities (SEEDS¹, SERCIDA², SaW³), in particular most recent such as SaW Country reports⁴ and National Development Plan documents⁵ are taken into account while assessing the national situation in 2018, with an emphasis on change and progress made.

2. Monitoring activities in 2018

A monitoring system is established and available to CESSDA for purposes of future continuous monitoring, as has been planned in the CESSDA strategies. Monitoring will be based on a regular short interview / survey of CESSDA Partners and other contacts established in non-member countries. A living document folder for each country will be established, which will be continuously updated. CESSDA Web page on partner countries may contain reference to the national reports. The first monitoring activity will be organised within this project. The report on recent developments will sum up information gathered at the workshops and other occasions, and from the monitoring.

2.1 Methods used for collecting information

Method for collecting information is semi-structured interviews. Interview structure and protocol are based on the work done in CESSDA SAW project Deliverable 3.2⁶ and updated to match the needs of this project. Reports and presentations at different widening events in 2018 are used as additional source of information on countries.

¹ <https://seedsproject.ch/>

² <http://www.serscida.eu/>

³ <http://cessdasaw.eu/>

⁴ http://cessdasaw.eu/content/uploads/2017/11/D3.2_CESSDA_SaW_v1.3.pdf

⁵ http://cessdasaw.eu/content/uploads/2017/11/D3.4_CESSDA_SaW_v1.0.pdf

⁶ http://cessdasaw.eu/content/uploads/2017/11/D3.2_CESSDA_SaW_v1.3.pdf

2.2 Scope of countries and folders structure

ADP prepared a preliminary list of possible countries for the monitoring task. At the project meeting in Milano project group went through whole list. 22 countries were chosen (those that have possible contact/response).

Folders were created for each partner, with subfolders for their responsible countries. In each country folder there is a part of the Deliverable 3.2 from SAW project (containing information regarding development potentials) that is linked to specific country. Versions in Word and PDF are both available⁷.

Partners used the specific folder for a specific country, and saved collected information there. It was up to partner to decide if they will share that folder with their interviewees or you just send them the documents.

A list of countries was chosen and distributed between 5 partners in this task (ADP, CSDA, FORS, SND, and TARKI) in June 2018. Division is presented in the table below.

Surveys countries by responsible partner

Responsible partner	Country	No.
ADP	Albania	1
	Croatia	2
	Ireland	3
	Kosovo	4
	Serbia	5
CSDA	Montenegro	6
	Slovakia	7
	Ukraine	8
FORS	Bosnia and Herzegovina	9
	Cyprus	10
	Luxembourg	11
	Macedonia	12
SND	Estonia	13
	Iceland	14
	Latvia	15
	Lithuania	16
	Russia	17
TARKI	Belgium	18
	Bulgaria	19
	Italy	20
	Poland	21
	Romania	22

⁷ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1IRiGtMblIVZdUkyE2LPsxxgKM1F48v9Z1?usp=sharing>

Contact Info table⁸ from CESSDA SAW project was updated, so it includes also information on participants from Milano workshop⁹, EC's National contact point of reference on SI¹⁰ and OpenAIRE National Open Access desk¹¹.

Main contact persons table

Main contact persons:	
Ministry	Minister
Ministry	Main contact regarding international research infrastructures
Research agency (funding)	Main contact person
Repository / archive (potential SP)	Head / Director
Repository / archive (potential SP)	Main contact person
Research institution	Key researcher / representative
EC expert group on NP of reference on SI	
OpenAIRE representative	
Milano participant	

Information for each contact

Institution
Function / Title
Name
Address
Email
Phone
Website
Info. entered by

Contact info table has a subsection on reporting the contacts made that needs to be filled in by partners.

⁸ CESSDA ERIC internal document

⁹ <https://www.cessda.eu/widening2018/>

¹⁰ <http://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3477>

¹¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/72-noads>

3. Structure and content of the country reports (template)

Two to three pages long report per country will be prepared. Length depends on the results of the interview and other available information. On general, it will follow the following structure.

Use font Arial, size 12, spacing 6pt after paragraph, and line spacing multiple "1.15".

Project	CESSDA Widening 2018
Document	Country report - XXXX
Date	XX/XX/2018
Interviewee	Name, position
Responsible CESSDA SP	XXXXX
Interviewer	Name, position
Abstract: XXXXX	

Introduction

Focus: Relevant areas of expertise of interviewees and overview of document sources and past activities/outcomes

Block A: Development of social sciences sector in the country

Focus: Funding capacities, human resources and infrastructure, international collaboration and national studies as driver of data production in the country.

Block B: RDM policy and support setting

Conclusion:

Links to relevant documents:

Note: Before publishing final report, the country experts should be invited to give comments. If no comments received in a week time, we will publish the report as it is. All project partners are invited to comment on final drafts.

Appendix 1: Guidelines and communication protocol for interviewers

A. General introduction to data collection methods, roles and principles

This section provides some suggestions on how to conduct the data collection process.

Step 1: Desk research to consult the existing sources of information

Partner responsible for a country, in preparation for the interview, consults available previous reports about the country, in order to be able to focus on relevant aspects where change is expected, to address key problems that persist from additional angles (e.g. needs about CESSDA support), and to avoid repeating the same information contained in previous reports while conducting the interviews (step 2 and 3). Desk research includes both a review of some official sources (like policy documents, statistical data) as well as a literature review (articles, reports and similar), and should be limited to the country in question. Main sources to consult are results and reports from previous Widening activities (SEEDS¹², SERCIDA¹³, SaW¹⁴), in particular most recent such as SaW Country reports¹⁵ and National Development Plan documents¹⁶, the 'EU Access to and preservation of scientific information in Europe. Report on the implementation of Commission Recommendation C (2012) 4890 final – Study¹⁷', and National Open Access, Open science policy statements and RI roadmaps.

Result of the desk research is an updated list of main document sources about the country past activities and situations. Short summary of the barriers and opportunities for establishment of sustainable DAS with key existing document sources, identified in previous rounds of monitoring activities, is to be included in the introduction of current report. Selection of interviewees (step 2) and adaptation of interview schedule (step 3) are both based on conclusions from desk research.

Step 2: Semi-structured interview process

Selection and contact:

Partner responsible for the country, identifies and selects relevant interviewee(s) among contacts of stakeholders (policy makers, research data expert, OpenAIRE and other OA people, etc.) following respondent selection guidelines specified in [B. Protocol for selection of interviewees and communication Guidelines](#);

¹² <https://seedsproject.ch/>

¹³ <http://www.sercida.eu/>

¹⁴ <http://cessdasaw.eu/>

¹⁵ http://cessdasaw.eu/content/uploads/2017/11/D3.2_CESSDA_SaW_v1.3.pdf

¹⁶ http://cessdasaw.eu/content/uploads/2017/11/D3.4_CESSDA_SaW_v1.0.pdf

¹⁷ <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/676f8a3b-62f6-11e8-ab9c-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

Step 3: Tailoring semi-structured interview protocol for country and stakeholder specific collection of information

After consulting past sources and based on them, the semi-structured interview questionnaire for the stakeholder is adapted by partner responsible for the country. Following the [section C \(Interview Guide for semi-structured interviews with experts\)](#) where main themes and question blocks are described, by focusing on country specifics and type of stakeholder, relevant issues, and corresponding questions are selected and adapted by the partner responsible for the country. This consists of taking out questions that are not relevant to the interviewees expertise, or to the country based on previously consulted sources; or additional clarification is requested for certain aspects that are relevant.

Step 4: Contact and carry on interview, collect information

Potential interviewees are contacted with request to answer to the e-mail interview with questions from step 3. If needed, an appropriate mode of extended interview data collection event (personal, Skype, telephone, e-mail exchange etc.) is agreed upon and clarifications are requested.

Each contact according to the communication protocol needs to be recorded in the Contact list.

When needed, interviews could be recorded; audio recording is recommended mostly in face-to-face interviews with nobody taking notes; the recording should be seen as a source for preparing the written interview summary.

The preferred interview language is English, short interview summary of answers to the interview questions in one document should also be in English;

The summary and direct quotes, which are used in the reports, are send to the interviewee for review and acceptance.

B. Protocol for selection of interviewees and communication, including the initial contact e-mail template

1 A motivation for collaboration

1.1 Semi-structured interview // Communication protocol

The initial contact (email) should include a brief description of the CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project and CESSDA, as well as goals to achieve with the data collection, and the optimal profile or characteristics of respondents.

Primarily the email should be sent to the director of the DAS or the contact person for CESSDA Widening activities if any is mentioned in the [CESSDA contact list](#).

1.1.1 Data Archive Services (potential SP): directors or Widening contact person

Dear colleague

We kindly invite you, as a contact person of a (national) research data service, to take part in our interview. This study is carried out by CESSDA ERIC in the internal CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project. The aim of CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project is to continue widen CESSDA as the European infrastructure for social science data archives with new members. Brief descriptions of the CESSDA, CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project, and the purpose of the interview are provided further below.

In case you are not in the position to respond, please, let us know as soon as possible who we may contact instead of you in your organisation.

Participation is voluntary and you may withdraw at any time. By participating you agree that the information provided will be made accessible through publications and reports of the CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project and beyond.

1.2 Semi-structured interview// Communication protocol

Instructions: **Two distinct strategies** of interviewee selection apply.

1. Countries with (proto) active DAS: Representative of DAS is primary interviewee candidate. Partners may ask the DAS representative to indicate the most appropriate organisation or person to contact for an additional interview.
2. Other countries (and if needed, this applies to countries of the first category): the experts may be identified during the desk research. In most countries, the preliminary contacts are already contained in the Contact Info table¹⁸ from CESSDA SAW project. Also, partners can ask different organisations (OpenAIRE national open access desks, faculties/research institutes in the social sciences, funding institutions, ministry/state agencies in charge of social sciences) to give the contact information of

¹⁸ CESSDA ERIC internal document

1 or 2 experts from within the social science research community. The semi-structured interview will be conducted with informants who have a particularly good view of the social science research community in their respective countries.

The expert, someone recognised for her/his important role in the national social science landscape could be a:

- Senior researcher in the social sciences working in a public research institution in the social sciences;
- Dean or her/his representative of a faculty of social sciences;
- Representative of the main funding institution in the social sciences and/or the open data movement (i.e. research councils or national science foundations);
- Representative of the ministry or state agency in charge of research in the social sciences.

Interview with one expert can be extended to one or two additional interviews. The selection of new expert could be on one of the two grounds: if certain topics are missing and you need to collect additional information on, or if you want to cross check some of the information collected already with another person for accuracy.

Contacts are to be made by email/phone by CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 partners. The initial contact (by email) should include a brief description of the CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project, of CESSDA, and task goals to achieve with the data collection and, if no name has been given by the SPs or desk research, the ideal profile or characteristics of the interviewee (i.e. expert in the social sciences... as described above).

1.2.1 Countries with (proto)active DAS

Dear Mrs or Mr

We recognize that you play an important role in the social science landscape in your country on the national level, therefore we kindly ask you to take part in an interview. This study is carried out by CESSDA AS and its partners in the CESSDA Widening 2018 project. The aim of CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project is to strengthen and widen CESSDA as the European infrastructure for social science data archives. Brief descriptions of the CESSDA, CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project, and the purpose of the survey are provided further below.

Participation is voluntary and you may withdraw at any time. By participating you agree that the information provided will be made accessible through publications and reports of the CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project and beyond.

If you believe that we should contact another expert or your colleague, please let us know as soon as possible and suggest who we may contact instead.

Please, confirm your participation by replying to this email, and indicate when we can expect to receive answers to the attached interview questions by email, or if you prefer that we contact you in other mode. Also, please indicate, which mode (personal, Skype,

telephone, e-mail exchange etc.) would you prefer for the extended interview, if clarifications are requested. We would appreciate to finalise the interview by **date [two-week time latest]**.

1.2.2 Other countries: adapt above

2 A brief description of CESSDA

CESSDA (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives - see more on <http://cessda.eu/>) is a pan-European Research Infrastructure that coordinates activities of social science data archives across Europe. The aim is to promote the results of social science research, in particular re-use of research data, and thereby to support national and international research and cooperation. CESSDA achieves its goals collectively by its members facilitating researchers' access to important data resources of relevance to the European social science research agenda regardless of the location of either researcher or data.

Currently CESSDA membership consists of 16 national state members and 1 observer. The aim is to achieve full European coverage, to strengthen the network and to ensure sustainability of its data for the widened network.

3 A brief description of the CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 project

Between 2015 and 2017, widening activities were covered within the CESSDA SaW Horizon 2020 project. **The CESSDA Widening Activities 2018** project aims to build on recent results of the aforementioned project and ensure the continuity of CESSDA widening efforts. CESSDA will maintain its network of CESSDA Partners, aspiring non-member service providers from the CESSDA SaW project, and increase its visibility in non-member countries.

4 Conclusions

So, let us once again invite you to take part in the interview, which will help us to gain an update on recent situation in different countries, and will help with organising further steps to achieve the goals of CESSDA as a true Pan-European Research Infrastructure.

For any further information please contact me as CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 partner responsible for country data collection!

CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 partner name.

CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 partner Institution + phone, email...

Final note

Information about persons participating must to be included in the CESSDA contact list template for each person (be it contact person, respondent or interviewee). If something changes in planning, and new interviewees or additional contact persons are planned, this should be added to a list of contacts.

Each main contact person that we attempt to contact should be listed at the Main contact persons section of a CESSDA contact list. For planning purposes, each contact should first be assigned to the 'Planned' in a 'Status of contact' of the Follow-up section of the contact list, with a 'Date planned' when the contact will be attempted. Specific CESSDA Widening Activities 2018 'Task 2' reference should be made at the 'Purpose of contact', followed by the role (Contact person, Interviewee, Respondent). Notes could be used for any additional information regarding a contact, e.g. which section a Respondent or Interviewee would be assigned, a timeline of contact attempts if more than one, until the final status of a contact is reached (either 'Answered', 'Transferred' or 'No answer'), visible in a Status of contact.

C. Interview Guide for semi-structured interviews with experts: content areas, indicator/related question blocks and issues to be addressed

Don't forget to refer to separate country report document in country folder. You might want to send it to your interviewee.

Parts:

Introduction

Development of social sciences sector in the country

RDM policy and support setting

Data sharing culture

Data infrastructure (where no formal DAS exists)

Abbreviation

Interview will serve as a basis for the (2-3 pages) public report that will be published on the CESSDA web site. Please inform interviewee about this.

Please ask interviewee to provide links to documents/reports (if English, otherwise national language) that are referred to in the interview.

When establishing contact do mention that interview is part of CESSDA Widening project and we would like to continue this kind of monitoring in the future.

Introduction

Focus: relevant areas of expertise

[Remark to the interviewer: At the beginning of the interview, the interviewer should inform the interviewee that the answers to these questions should cover whole SSH sector in his/her country and that he/she should answer the questions from his/her knowledge or experience.]

Themes:

- consent for participation and agreement or not on publishing name of the interviewee in the report
- interviewee's background/ areas of expertise, academic/other working position;
- academic and related achievements;
- research experience;
- knowledge / experience of RIs.

Block A: Development of social sciences sector in the country

Focus:

Funding capacities, human resources and infrastructure, international collaboration and national studies as driver of data production in the country.

Themes:

- development of research data production in SSH in the country;
- existence of national studies as an incentive for data production;
- volume and frequency of data production in SSH in the country;
- assessment of quality of produced data in SSH in the country.

Questions:

- Please assess the needs and demand for social science data services based on estimation of size and other characteristics of the SSH researchers community data produced and used.
- Based on estimates of quality and variety of data that is produced under different funding arrangements (Government sector, Business enterprise sector, Abroad, Private non-profit sector, Higher education sector): Could you assess the existence of sufficient quality and variety of data that deserve data services to be built upon, to ensure preservation and wide access?
- Do the public policy makers in your country make decisions based on evidence?

[Remark to the interviewer: Interviewee should be encouraged to give additional remarks about attitudes of government authorities toward the usefulness of the academic research for the policy decision making that incentivise the re-use of existing data.

Based on the previous reports and other desk-resources about the country social science research landscape, address the question about the past and current research data preservation and encourage to estimate the 'cost of inaction', if the valuable research data might probably be lost. If so, provide example and illustrate. Refer here to Beagrie model: estimate of value of data service compared to cost associated.

Recent work by Beagrie et al.¹⁹ demonstrates the benefits of national data services. Two Worksheets can be referred to for self-evaluation of the feasibility of the data archive project in a country (the Archive Development Canvas, and the Benefits Summary for a Data Archive).]

¹⁹ CESSDA SaW Cost-Benefit Advocacy Toolkit, Charles Beagrie Ltd and CESSDA 2017, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18448/16.0013>.

Block B: RDM policy and support setting

Focus:

Policies for data documentation and management facilitating data sharing and ethical and legal framework.

Themes:

- explore overarching strategy and policy to enable sustainable data access and sharing of publicly financed SSH data;
- general situation regarding requirements or recommendations concerning the preparation of a Data Management Plan (DMP);
- research funding organization's requirements or recommendations about preserving quality-assured social science research data with associated metadata;
- RDM policy requirements: sustainability and long term curation;
- incentives for data sharing: covering costs in the country for managing the data resourced;
- costs of inaction – research data being lost;
- Ethical and Legal framework important for data sharing;
- general situation in a country with regard to clarification and support provided on legal and ethical aspects that facilitate social science data sharing.

Questions:

Explore overarching strategy and policy to enable sustainable data access and sharing of publicly financed SSH data

- How would you characterize the general situation with regard to requirements or recommendations regarding the preparation of Data Management Plans (DMP) as an integral part of funding applications and of on-going project activity? Is open science policy aiming at Open data as the default among public funders of SSH research in your country?
- To what extent have public research funding organizations operating in your country issued requirements or recommendations about quality-assured SSH research data with associated metadata? Do they require the researcher to offer or deposit the data in an appropriate disciplinary repository?
- To what extent are funders and journals in your country requiring that data be deposited at repositories and made available to researchers for secondary use and replication? Are there any existing archives and repositories available to store and disseminate data? Are some valuable national data resources at risk?
- What are the public research funding organizations vision and action regarding the organisation of research data infrastructure in the country? Are FAIR principles mentioned? Are disciplinary data services mentioned in research infrastructure roadmaps? Are trusted repository requirements set for data infrastructure? Is international interoperability required?

[Remark to the interviewer: If the answer cannot be specified in detail, the interviewer should proceed with the following question: Is there an intention or awareness to address research data management and sharing in any form and on any level of public funder policy or strategy or principles declaration? Please describe and refer to specific examples!]

- What incentives for sharing research data with associated metadata do the public research funding organizations operating in your country provide? Do they cover costs for managing and preparing data, facilitate citation of data and rewards based on the impact, etc.?

- Is there a data policy at (EU), national and institutional level that sets expectations or requirements for research data management and sharing, with funding for data management and infrastructure/support development in your country?

Ethical and Legal framework important for data sharing

- How would you characterize the general situation in your country with regard to clarification and support provided on legal and ethical aspects that facilitate SSH data sharing (IPR, data protection...)?

[Remark to the interviewer: Please describe and refer to specific recent examples or documents (include reference in the report)! References to GDPR and issues about archiving and sharing scientific or cultural content under copyright could be mentioned and who are the players that provide guidance to researchers.]

Block C: Data sharing culture

Focus:

Behaviour/ practices, attitudes and perceived barriers and incentives for data sharing, RDM support and practices

Themes:

- enablers for data sharing;
- data support services and RDM practices.

Questions:

Enablers for data sharing

- How common it is for researchers in your country to publish in journals that expect data used in the publication to be available for reuse from a trusted digital repository? If it is common, which are those journals?
- In your country and within the SSH research discipline(s), could you say whether there are careers rewards related to data sharing? If yes
 - What influence, if any, may sharing research data have on career progression within institution or community or due to government rules? Is there any career progression in academia as a motive for data sharing?
 - What about the success rate in obtaining research funding?
 - What about better standing within the research community and other.

Data support services and RDM practices

- What cooperative and shared data support services that facilitate data sharing and OA to research data are available in the in your country in different stages of research project?
- Describe the availability of data infrastructure, the availability of support services and tools (e.g. trainings, workshops, webinars, online reference materials, help desk or other consultancy, etc.) given to researchers from libraries or other institutions regarding, for example, data management plans, data preservation, and data access.
- In your country, how do researchers in your research area manage and document the data to facilitate data reuse?
- What standards do they use, and what procedures in data management they follow to facilitate data reuse?

Block D: Data infrastructure (where no formal CESSDA ERIC member SP exists)

Focus:

Assessment of functioning data archive or of activities to develop a data archive. Focus more on open access support activities and on planning of future DAS in countries where no formal DAS exists yet.

Themes

- institutionalisation of DAS proto-activities;
- availability of technical infrastructure;
- existence of organisational activities;
- availability of capacity building and training;
- open access (OA) support activities;
- availability of OA projects or initiatives;
- cooperation with OpenAIRE National Open Access Desks (NOAD);

[Instruction to the interviewer: Between the non CESSDA members countries the DAS activities are on different development level. Assess and characterize before interview, what are the most typical features of the DAS activities in the country?

- *is this a kind of proto-activities or*
- *are there established but poor/underdeveloped infrastructure activities*
- *or a well-developed institution is working in the country but for other reason (for example lack of stakeholder supports) country failed to reach the ERIC member status?*

In addition, a reference can be made to the NDP for countries that participated in SaW 3.3²⁰ activity. These are: Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Kosovo, Latvia, Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, and Ukraine.

Please, try to take notice / highlight the questions relevant in the case of the country regarding to the characterisation of DAS above]

Questions

Institutionalisation of DAS proto-activities

(non-NDP countries)

- Are there existing technical infrastructures (such as repositories, online tools, databases, or online catalogues, etc.) in your country that could possibly be used for or applied to a new data archive service (DAS)? Also, is it planned to use them for a future DAS?
- Are there any activities in your country towards establishing a DAS for the social sciences? Have you considered the starting points, conditions, required key resources, partners, data depositors/users, beneficiaries, services/activities, cost structure/financing schemes? Have you found any potential funding partners? Have you organized any infrastructure preparatory activities, such as round tables, lectures, workshops, report, feasibility studies? Would you consider following the model of preparing National Development Plan for DAS in your country beneficial?
- Are there institutions that could host a DAS in your country? Which institution(s) could host the future data service?

(NDP countries)

- Which of the planned features of the data services have been realized? Have you fulfilled required financial, human, expert resources/needs? Would you emphasize any good and/or bad experiences? Which challenges did you encounter and how did you resolve them? Have you been engaged in advocacy activities?

²⁰ http://cessdasaw.eu/content/uploads/2017/11/D3.4_CESSDA_SaW_v1.0.pdf

(All types of countries)

- What skills/expertise and knowledge are required to establish the service? Does the staff, someone in the host institution or in the country already have it? How to develop the knowledge and skills? Is there a local/international partner that could play this role? Are there existing initiatives in your country to develop the knowledge and skills of people who might at some point be employed at a DAS? This could include research and data management (mainly data management plan), data preservation, and data access. Would you consider to contact CESSDA Training Group to offer training in this regard?
- Are the potential funding partners reliable? What would be their funding conditions? Would the funding be secured? For how long? Is the funding based on projects? What lobbying activities have been carried on?

Open access (Open science) support activities

- Are there open access projects or initiatives in your country, either funded by the government or by grassroots?

[Remark to the interviewer: You might want to address EC report on the implementation of Commission Recommendations C (2012) 4890 "Access to and preservation of scientific information in Europe"²¹]

Questions

Promising established infrastructure with periodic or persistent activities

- Please, tell us some words about your plan how to develop the data infrastructure in your country?
- Tell us about the missing resources to reach the above mentioned plan (human, financial, technical, stakeholders' support, poor data sharing culture, etc.)?
- Which is the current main gap to reach the next step in the development plan? What do you think, what is the main long term requirement to operate a DAS in your country?
- What kind of technical development is needed to approach the development plan in the DAS?
- What are the main reasons for lack of the financial support in your country? Lack of inland or international project possibilities? Permanent institutional resources to employ full-time staff? In-kind type of needs (i.e. permanent office, technical environment, etc.)? Lack of information to implement international standards? Any other reason?
- Please, describe in more detail the above mentioned needs regarding the financing/technical/etc. aspect of the DAS in your country?
- Tell us about other needs not mentioned in the above answers!

Established national data service seeking support for becoming full CESSDA members

- Please, describe the main reason why the country did not reach the member status in the CESSDA ERIC so far and nominate the Service provider? (e.g. Administrative reasons/lack of support/financial problems/technical gaps/etc.)
- Administrative reasons: What kind of needs do you have to support the joining to the ERIC? Would you need any administrative help and guidance?
- Stakeholders' aspect: Is there a stakeholder's support in your country for becoming full CESSDA member? Is the CESSDA well known organization in your country among different stakeholders (e.g. researcher community, research institutions, funders, policy

²¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/openaccess/npr_report.pdf

makers)? If they do not provide enough support for CESSDA membership, what are the reasons?

- Financing aspects: are there any financing support missing to reach the membership? Please, describe briefly the main difficulties regarding financing situation, if any, for fulfilling the CESSDA membership obligations.
- Technical aspects? Is the technical infrastructure you are running developed up to the requirements to join the CESSDA ERIC? Is there any technical lack to reach the membership? Please, describe the DAS needs regarding these technical challenges.
- Please, describe other lacks in your country? What is limiting the DAS to reach the ERIC membership status?

Organisational profile

[Remark to the interviewer: If SaW Country reports²² already contain information on the Organisational profile, ask about what new and recent services and activities have been introduced in recent year, or are planned for the following year.

For countries that did not participated in SaW Country report activities, Questions could be ether on the activities the DAS provides, or if some services are missing or are planned for the following years, what are those activities planned.

For countries for which National Development Plan document²³ exist, this can be used as a reference, asking about update and prioritisation of planned services and activities, and what has been eventually realised since NDP writing]

- Please describe core services and activities that are offered by the data archive service.
- Please describe how the data archive service is funded:

Whether it is fully, partly publicly, or privately funded, and/or share of project-based funding vs. long-term contractual funding (example: 100 % public funding, through Research Council and Government Ministry funding).

[Remark to the interviewer: Again as for recent update on situation, if previous reports contain some information already, or ask about what is planned and under discussion]

- Physical and administrative location of the data archive service. (e.g. part of university/housed within a larger organisation, etc.)

Also: describe relationship to other suppliers/partners that are of importance to the national provision of services (if applicable).

- Please provide a brief description of the overall contents of the current collection, i.e. subjects, types of data, etc.
- Please define primary and secondary user communities (if applicable):

²² http://cessdasaw.eu/content/uploads/2017/11/D3.2_CESSDA_SaW_v1.3.pdf

²³ http://cessdasaw.eu/content/uploads/2017/11/D3.4_CESSDA_SaW_v1.0.pdf